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Research Article

Comparative study of Morphological Variation in Placenta between Normal and Pregnancy Induced Hypertension (PIH) Patients.

Shilpa Patle¹, Jayashree Mhaisekar², Roshni Yavale³, Amit Nakanekar³

¹Post Graduate student, Department of Sharir Rachna (Anatomy), Government Ayurved College, Nagpur.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Sharir Rachna (Anatomy), Government Ayurved College, Nagpur

³Assistant Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa (Medicine), Government Ayurved College, Nagpur

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ABSTRACT

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Background- Placenta has nutritive, excretory, hormonal and various other important functions in fetal life. It is bridge between maternal metabolism and fetal metabolism. Various metabolic disorders may also influence placenta. Pregnancy induced Hypertension (PIH) is also one of such commonly occurring metabolic disorder.

Methodology- In the present study we have observed morphological variations in placenta of normal delivery and placenta of PIH patients after their delivery.

Results There was statistically significant decrease in diameter of PIH (14.96 ± 1.16) than normal (19.46 ± 1.52), statistically significant decrease in area of PIH (173.65 ± 20.90 sq cm) than normal (286.81 ± 52.82 sq.cm) statistically significant decrease in number of cotyledons of PIH (15.03 ± 1.21) than normal (22.33 ± 3.60) $P < 0.01$. Bluish color of placenta was observed in all the cases of PIH, and only normal placenta was bluish maximum of normal placenta were whitish.

Conclusion PIH has its remarkable effects on morphology of placenta in terms of reduction in weight, changes in color, hardness, reduced numbers of cotyledons on maternal surface. PIH is also responsible more number of LSCS than normal ANC females.

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Amit Nakanekar, Assistant Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa (Medicine), Government Ayurved College, Nagpur

INTRODUCTION:

The placenta is an organ that develops in the uterus and provides oxygen and nutrients to the fetus and remove the waste product from the baby's blood. In short it performs nutritive, excretory and respiratory function. It produces necessary hormones to maintain pregnancy and provides immunity. ⁽¹⁾ With such a substantial role in development of the fetus, deformity in development of placenta can hamper further natural development of the fetus. This issue is of serious concern.

Placenta is a circular disc. At its center it has a thickness of 3cm and diameter of 15 -20 cm. It has thin border at the edge and has spongy feeling all over the placenta. It weighs about 500 gm. Weight of placenta and weight of baby are in a ratio of 1:6. ⁽²⁾

Placenta has two surfaces. Fetal surface is covered by glistening amnion with the umbilical cord attached at or near its center. Maternal surface of placenta with tinge of dull reddish in Color with rough and spongy appearance. Thin layer with grayish Color which is somewhat shaggy is the remnant of the decidua basalis which is compact and spongy. The maternal surface is divided into 15-20 lobes which are convex and polygonal known as cotyledons. Each cotyledon is separated from other by a fissure. ⁽³⁾

Many further factor can affect the overall functioning of placenta such as maternal age, high blood pressure and substance abuse problems etc. One of the common complication observed in the pregnancy is "Hypertension". It causes significantly to maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. ⁽⁴⁾ Thus high prevalence of PIH in India i.e. 15.2.⁽⁵⁾ in the pregnant women in the present era the present study aims at observing morphological variation occurring in the placenta of PIH patient other than normal pregnant women.

AIM

To Compare Morphological Variation of Placenta between Normal and PIH Patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

After Ethical approval from Institutional ethics committee Government Ayurved College, Nagpur. (GACN); A observational study was conducted on 60

Patients of full term delivery. They were divided in two groups of 30 patients each; section of patients was done from IPD of *Streeroga* and *Prasutitantra* department of GACN hospital and IPD of Gynecology and Obstetrics department of Medical College Hospital, Nagpur (GMCN).

Group A included 30 placentas of normal PNC patients and Group B included 30 placentas of PIH PNC patients having sign and symptoms irrespective of age, gravid status, method of delivery i.e. Vaginal and LSCS.

Pathological conditions of placenta like Placenta accrete, Placenta Previa, abruptio placentae, Placentitis etc., History of any other abnormality/disease during pregnancy, Twins and multiple pregnancies, Preterm and Post term labor, Unmarried patients and Un-Co-operative patients were excluded.

Information regarding sign and symptoms of patients from both the groups was noted. The parameters for assessment i.e. Weight, Diameter, Texture, Color, Surface area, shape, Insertion of Umbilical cord, No. of Cotyledons were collected and filled up in Case Report Form.

After delivery, individual placenta was taken in tray and observational clinical study was done in following steps-

- At first, Weight of placenta was measured with the help of weighing machine.
- Diameter of placenta was measured with the help of measuring tape in centimeters.
- Texture of placenta was felt by fingers of hand. When it felt smooth fleshy like mass, then it was noted as soft and when it felt some cotyledons calcified, then it was noted as moderately hard. When fingers felt more than half of cotyledons calcified, and then it was noted as hard.
- Color was observed, fetal as well as maternal side with the help of naked eyes.
- Shape was observed with the help of naked eyes.
- Surface area was calculated with the help of mathematical formulae
- Firstly, maternal side was opened, then cotyledons were counted by numbering method.

Dissection of normal PNC's Placenta

Initially, placental fetal membrane was removed with the help of scalpel and forcep. Then chorionic plate of Placenta was seen. Bifurcated vessels of umbilical cord were seen. After that amniotic membrane of small portion of fetal surface was removed with the help of scalpel and forceps. There was bifurcation of umbilical vessels.

Then, fetal membrane on maternal side was removed with the help of scalpel and forceps. Maternal blood was identified. Deep to this blood, maternal surface was divided into number of small lobules called maternal cotyledons by deep sulci. Deep to this, it was difficult to identify any structure with the help of naked eyes.

Dissection of PIH PNC's Placenta

At first, with the help of scalpel and forcep placental fetal membrane was removed. Then chorionic plate of placenta was seen. It was more bluish in colour as compared to normal placenta. Bifurcation vessels of umbilical cord were seen. The amniotic membrane of small portion of fetal surface was removed with the help of scalpel and forcep. There was bifurcation of umbilical vessels. Deep to this, it was difficult to identify any structure with the help of naked eyes. Then, on maternal side fetal membrane was removed with the help of scalpel and forceps. Maternal blood was identified. Deep to this blood, maternal surface was divided into number of small lobules called maternal cotyledons by deep sulci. As compare to normal PNC's placenta, maternal cotyledons were large in size and small in number.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

In table No. 1 and graph No. 1 and image no.1 Normal PNC shows greater variation than PIH PNC in weight

of Placenta. Which was statistically significant with p value <0.05 . From table No. 2 and graph No. 2 it was seen that there is no significant difference found in Fetoplacental weight ratio between Normal and PIH PNC having $p >0.05$. From table no.3 and graph No.3 and image no. 2 it was seen that Diameter of Placenta in Normal PNC shows greater variation than in PIH PNC which was statistically significant with $p <0.01$. From table no. 4 , graph No. 4 image no. 2 it was observed that Normal PNC shows greater variation than PIH PNC in Surface Area of Placenta with $p <0.01$. From table no. 5 ,graph no. 5 and image no. 3 it was observed that there was considerably extremely significant difference observed in No. of Cotyledons of placenta in Normal PNC and PIH PNC. Thus the no. of cotyledons in placenta of PIH patients is less which is statistically significant with $p <0.01$. From table no. 6 and graph no.6, maximum patients were from LSCS as population distribution. Table no. 7 and graph no. 7 shows that maximum patients had moderately hard placenta. From table no. 8 and graph no. 8 it was observed that insertion of Umbilical cord maximum at near to central as population distribution. Table no. 9 ,graph no. 9 and image no. 4 indicate that Color of placenta of chorionic plate in most of the normal PNC is more whitish and less bluish and image no 5 shows that in PIH PNC bluish Color placenta. Table no. 10 and graph no. 10 and image no. 6 shows that color of placenta of maternal plate in normal and PIH has dull red and dark red respectively. From Table no 11, graph no. 11 and image no 2 it is observed that there is maximum disc shaped and round shaped placenta in normal and PIH PNC. Table no. 12 and graph no. 12 shows that maximum no. of patient were having gestational PIH.

Graph No. 1 Showing distribution according to weight of Placenta

Table No. 1 Distribution according to weight of Placenta.

No	Weight of Placenta	Mean ± SD	SEM	t value	p value
1	Normal PNC	502.00 ± 63.51	11.60	2.965	< 0.05
2	PIH women	467.16 ± 17.30	03.15		

Graph No. 2 showing distribution according to Fetoplacental Weight Ratio

Table No. 2 distribution according to Fetoplacental Weight Ratio.

No	Feto Placental weight ratio	Mean ± SD	SEM	t value	p value
1	Normal PNC	5.45 ± 1.04	0.19	1.741	>0.05
2	PIH PNC	4.98 ± 1.06	0.19		

Graph No.3 Showing distribution according to Diameter of placenta

Table No3: Distribution according to Diameter of placenta

No	Diameter	Mean ± SD	SEM	t value	p value
1	Normal PNC	19.46 ± 1.52	0.27	12.86	<0.01
2	PIH PNC	14.96 ± 1.16	0.21		

Graph No.4 Showing distribution according to Surface Area of Placenta

Table No 4. distribution according to Surface Area of Placenta

No	Surface area(sq.cm)	Mean ± SD	SEM	t value	p value
1	Normal PNC	286.81 ± 52.82	9.64	10.90	<0.01
2	PIH PNC	173.65 ± 20.90	3.81		

Graph No.5 Showing distribution according to Number of cotyledons of Placenta.

Table No5. Number of cotyledons of Placenta.

No	No. of Cotyledons	Mean ± SD	SEM	t value	p value
1	Normal PNC	22.33 ± 3.60	0.65	10.36	<0.01
2	PIH PNC	15.03 ± 1.21	0.22		

Graph No.6 Showing Distribution of normal PNC and PIH PNC according to type of labour

Table No.6 Distribution of normal PNC and PIH PNC according to type of labour

Type of labour	Normal PNC	PIH PNC	Total
	No. of patient	No. of patient	
FTND	17	8	25
LSCS	13	22	35

Graph No.7 Showing Distribution according to texture of placenta

Table No.7 Distribution according to texture of placenta

Sr. No	Texture	Normal PNC No. of patient	PIH PNC No. of patients	Total
1	Soft	12	8	20
2	Moderately hard	14	21	35
3	Hard	4	1	5

Graph No. 8 Showing Distribution according to Insertion of Umbilical cord

Table No.8 Distribution according to Insertion of Umbilical cord

Sr. No.	Insertion Of Umbilical Cord	Normal PNC No. of patients	PIH PNC No. of patients	Total
1	Central	8	12	20
2	Near to Central	13	15	28
3	Periphery	9	3	12

Graph No.9 Showing distribution Colour of placenta of chorionic plate

Table No.9 Distribution according to Color of placenta of chorionic plate

Sr. No.	Appearance	Normal PNC No. of patient	PIH PNC No. of patients	Total
1	More whitish, less bluish	16	0	16
2	Less whitish, more bluish	9	0	9
3	more brightest	4	0	4
4	Bluish	1	30	31

Graph No. 10 Showing Distribution according Colour of placenta of maternal plate

Table No.10 Distribution according Colour of placenta of maternal plate

SNo.	Colour	Normal PNC No. of patients	PIH PNC No. of patient	Total
1	Dark Red	4	21	25
2	Dull Red	26	9	35

Graph No.11 Showing Distribution according to shape of placenta

Table No.11 Distribution Shape of placenta

Sr. No.	Shape	Normal PNC No. of patients	PIH PNC No. of patient	Total
1	Round	0	22	22
2	Disc shape	19	7	26
3	Oval	11	1	12

Graph No.12 Showing distribution according to type of PIH

Table No.12 Distribution according to Type of PIH patients

Sr. No	Type of PIH patients	No. of PIH patient
1	Gestational	19
2	Pre-Eclampsia	2
3	Eclampsia	9

Image No. 1

Image No. 2

Normal PNC's

PIH PNC placenta

Image No. 3

Image no. 4

Image No .5

Image No.6

DISCUSSION

In present study, it was found that in PIH patients the weight of placenta was lesser as compared to normal

range i.e. 500 gm. Also the diameter of placenta, surface area of placenta and no. of cotyledons were less in PIH group. Similar type of observations were

also found in various studies. Salmani D. et al. shows the result as the weight of placenta dimension were less in pre-eclampsia and eclampsia when compared with normal placenta.⁽⁶⁾ Nahar and his coworkers in their study, reported that microscopic study of placenta revealed placental weight, surface area of placenta and no. of cotyledons were less in study group (PIH patients).⁽⁷⁾ It may be due to endothelial dysfunction and vasospasm in uterus.⁽⁸⁾ Normally, within the 12 weeks of pregnancy there is cytotrophoblastic invasion into the spiral arteries, initially upto the intra-decidual portion. Endothelial lining is replaced as well as the musculo elastic media is destroyed and replaced by fibrinoid material. Secondary invasion of trophoblast extending upto the radial arteries within the myometrium occurs between the 12-16 weeks. Then spiral arteries get converted into large bore uteroplacental arteries. Due to this, funneling of arteries occurs which results into reduction of blood pressure to 70- 80 mmhg before it reaches the intervillous space. And increases the flow of blood.⁽⁹⁾

The second wave of endovascular trophoblast migration does not occurs, in the pre-eclampsia which leads to reduction in the blood supply to the fetoplacental unit.⁽¹⁰⁾

In the present study, color of placenta color of placenta of maternal plate was found bluish and dark red color respectively. It might be due to reduced blood supply to the placenta salmani D et al have also concluded about lesser blood supply this may also adversely affect fetal growth and development in cases of PIH patients. (6)

In this study, maximum female had a disc shaped placenta in normal PNC and round shaped in PIH PNC. Distribution of altered force may be the reason. Occurrence of L.S.C.S. is maximum in PIH patient as compare with normal PNC This difference is due to PIH being commonest indication of L.S.C.S. PIH can also causes fetal distress and hence, preference of more no. of L.S.C.S. can be seen in present study. Maximum women had moderately hard placenta. Comparatively, PIH increases the hardness of placenta. We cannot conclude any significant difference in insertion of umbilical cord on placenta between normal and PIH division. Larger size may

give different finding. In present study, gestational PIH is more.

CONCLUSION

PIH has its remarkable effects on morphology of placenta in terms of reduction in weight, changes in color, hardness, reduced numbers of cotyledons on maternal surface. PIH is also responsible more number of LSCS than normal ANC females.

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